

Challenges Encountered by the Kindergarten Teachers Using Printed Modular Instruction

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Abstract:

The study aimed to assess the challenges faced by kindergarten teachers in Tayasan Districts 1 and 2, Negros Oriental, in implementing printed modular instruction during the 2020–2021 school year. It examined variables such as plantilla position, length of service, and educational qualifications. The findings revealed that teachers with lower plantilla positions, shorter service years, and lower educational qualifications encountered significant challenges in distributing and retrieving modules, completing instructional materials, and assessing student progress. Notably, teachers in remote areas faced additional difficulties due to limited access to communication tools and unreliable transportation. Vice President Leni Robredo highlighted similar concerns nationwide, emphasizing that teachers should not bear the financial burden of printing and distributing learning materials. She advocated for reallocating the Department of Education's (DepEd) P29-billion budget for school rehabilitation to fund distance learning needs, including the procurement of gadgets and equipment, and to address health concerns for educators. The study concluded that while the challenges were significant, they were not insurmountable. It recommended that DepEd collaborate with local government units to provide transportation for module delivery and retrieval, allocate sufficient funds for the production of instructional materials, and ensure the availability of functional equipment. Additionally, it suggested that teachers utilize learners' profiles to assess and track student progress effectively.

Keywords: Challenges, Educational Qualifications, Kindergarten Teachers

Introduction:

It has been observed that during this pandemic (COVID-19), traditional face-to-face classroom setting is impossible to happen. As to solve the existing problem and not to skip the school year, a massive and abrupt change in the various modal standards of instructions has been introduced. The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines is on the process of adapting into the new form of educational delivery, kindergarten teachers have been encountering challenges that obstruct the attainment of objectives in education. The shift of teaching-learning in schools to printed modular learning has been made more challenging on Self-learning modules (SLM's) and Worksheets.

These materials like the SLM's and worksheets are tools for learners' engagement and attainment of learning goals; later, must consider the needs and interests of the learners. The modification of previous assessment guidelines such that they would suit to the non-face-to-face mode of teaching and learning. DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2020 entitled Interim Guidelines for Assessment and Grading in Light of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan was issued on October 2, 2020. Conversely, having been used to the previous assessment guidelines as stipulated in DepEd Order No. 8, series of 2015 entitled Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment in the K to 12 Basic

Education Program (BEP) that is still in effect, kindergarten teachers as expected find difficulties in conforming to the new guidelines. Such has been encompassed in the topics discussed during the Midyear In-Service Training (INSET) but no sufficient workshops have been supplemented. In line with that, DepEd Order No. 18 (2020) established guidelines on the release, utilization and liquidation of support funds for the printing and delivery of self-learning modules and other resources.

The researcher, being the kindergarten school teacher has observed that teachers were complaining on the content and organization of the self-learning modules. Such complaints were gathered and organized by the researcher into the research instrument to check if they were true to all the kindergarten teachers of Tayasan district 1 and 2 Division of Negros Oriental. It is in this light that the researcher is prompted to conduct a study in determining the challenges encountered by the kindergarten teachers in the implementation of printed modular instruction as basis for an intervention plan.

Current State of Knowledge

Challenges in Printed Modular Instructions. The theory that anchors this study is the Scaffolding (constructivist theory) by Jerome Bruner. Scaffolding refers to the steps taken to reduce the degrees of freedom in carrying out some task so that the child can concentrate on the difficult skill he/she is acquiring. It involves helpful, structured interaction between an adult (parents/guardian) and a child to help the child achieve a specific goal. It is the space for potential development, and it is the space where learning occurs; thus, where teaching needs to be situated (Pattalitan, 2016). This is the time for learners to engage in intellectually stimulating and demanding tasks. The problem is, what if mediocre materials are provided during this crucial period? In this case, learners' interactions with the materials while working independently would not let them acquire the necessary skills and knowledge to apply to new situations. Furthermore, the process of assessment in the new normal, which the kindergarten teachers are still experimenting with, also adds to the burden. The process of evaluating how much learning a learner has attained during the engagement period is also challenged by difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers. According to Beghetto (2018), the word challenge literally means an invitation or a call to action, the task, question, or issue one will address or solve. The shift of teaching-learning in schools to modular learning (kindergarten learners) is made more challenging on self-learning modules (alternative delivery mode) and assessment (worksheet). The success and effectiveness of modular distance learning depend on the design, development, and utilization of high-quality learning materials (Jayaram and Dorababu, 2015). These materials are tools for learners' engagement and attainment of learning goals; they must be student-centered, considering the needs and interests of the learners. Self-learning materials are based on the principles of self-learning (Rakes & Dunn, 2010, as cited by Maphosa et al., 2019). In developing such, it should provide kindergarten learners with helpful information and guides, enabling them to engage in independent learning. It must also be ensured that the distribution and retrieval of self-learning modules are considered. The main challenge that emerged was the lack of school funding for producing and delivering modules (Dangle & Sumaang, 2020).

While doing this distribution and retrieval, the Department also assured that the safety and health of teachers and personnel will be its top priority, as SLMs can be done at home. Teachers who would need to visit their schools to get materials to prepare the SLMs are required to follow the existing work arrangement and health protocols (DepEd, 2020).

In terms of retrieval, accomplished activity sheets will be retrieved by teachers from parents. They will have to submit the activity sheets to teachers in school or at designated pick-up points. This kind of setup, however, poses risks. Teachers and parents raised concerns over using the modular learning approach due to fears of contracting the coronavirus (Almario, 2020).

To improve the tracking scheme on retrieval, the division of Dasmariñas in Region IV-A Calabarzon issued Division Memorandum No. 178 s. 2020, dated September 15, 2020, entitled Additional Guidelines in the Distribution, Use, and Retrieval of Self-Learning Modules. Such additional guidelines are provided to improve access, maximize its use, and minimize or eliminate damages and/or losses (DM 178, 2020). It is emphasized in the said memorandum that upon returning the SLMs, the one in charge of receiving them shall check the SLMs by taking note of whether the number code matches the name of the learners who used the modules. Proper custodianship prescribed by the Department shall be observed since government funds were utilized to reproduce these materials.

In light of the completion of self-learning modules, it should be noted that engaging parents demands a deep reflexive attitude from the teacher—one that most likely develops through practice and meaningful internalization processes of knowledge. Beginning teachers need to be encouraged to develop a moral stance in relation to their professional responsibilities to meaningfully develop the ability and sensitivity to establish authentic partnerships with all parents (Lima & Kuusisto, 2019). The teacher's professional knowledge will reveal itself in pedagogical decisions that cannot be dissociated from his/her own principles and values. Since parents act as learning facilitators in ensuring that their children are indeed learning from the materials provided, parents must collaborate with teachers (or vice-versa) in meeting the learner's goals of the children (ADEC Innovations, 2019).

In terms of printing the modules for completion, both the young and old teachers are doing the job together; hence, both are challenged by the unavailability of equipment and end up purchasing a personal printer. The Teachers Dignity Coalition lamented the difficulty that teachers must face in printing modules and shouldering the cost of

equipment as well (CNN Philippines, 2020). Printers have a thousand reasons that can go wrong so soon after the purchase. Personal equipment, repairs, and parts replacements will have to be shouldered once again by the teachers.

In local news, Vice President Leni Robredo on Sunday echoed the concerns of some teachers' groups regarding the lack of resources and health risks in printing and distributing learning modules a day before classes start in public schools (CNN Philippines, 2020). Robredo shared the struggles of some teachers who have been burdened with the pressure of completing the distribution of printed modules, unlike the usual tradition of holding face-to-face classes. However, in most public schools, modules are printed equally by all teachers, regardless of age and sex (National Center for Education Statistics, 2020).

Theoretical Framework

The study is premised on Scaffolding, a key concept of Jerome Bruner's theory of learning and development. Bruner refers scaffolding as the steps taken to reduce the degrees of freedom in carrying out some task so that the child can concentrate on the difficult skill she is in the process of acquiring' (Bruner, 1978, p. 19) and updated by Dr. Saul Mcleod, 2019. Scaffolding involves helpful, structured interaction between an adult and a child with the aim of helping the child achieve a specific goal. The concept of scaffolding first is very similar to Vygotsky's notion of the zone of proximal development. Bruner believed that the most effective way to develop a coding system is to discover it rather than being told by the teacher. And as the distance between the actual development level (of a learner) as determined by independent problem solving and the level of potential development under adult guidance or in collaboration with more capable peers (Billings & Walqui, 2015).

The above statement implies that the actual development level of a learner and the next level attainable is mediated by a tool and a capable adult. In printed modular instruction, this tool refers to the self-learning material/alternative delivery mode and the capable adult refers to the learning facilitators which include parents/guardians, siblings and the community. Learners in kindergarten are considered to be Iconic (1-6 years old) where information is stored as sensory images (icons), usually visual ones, like pictures in mind. Thinking is also based on the use of other mental images (icons), such as hearing, smell or touch. For Bruner (1961), the purpose of education is not to impart knowledge, but to facilitate a child's thinking and problem-solving skills which can be transferred to a range of situations. Specifically, education should also develop symbolic thinking in children. Thus, learners are active learners who construct their own knowledge that this recent situation, new normal refers with our Self-learning materials and alternative delivery mode through the guidance and assistance of an adult that probably denotes as the parents and guardians.

They should be reminded when they can do alone to be able to complete the task individually. When learners can do without help, the need for assistance shrinks. Once they do not longer need the help, they are ready to establish autonomy in engaging activities that enable them to apply and modify what they have learned when they were yet guided. According to Patalitan, (2016) the space for potential development is the scaffolding and it is the space where learning occurs; thus where teaching need to be situated. This is the time for them to engage in intellectually stimulating and demanding tasks. In this pandemic time, this refers to the task of working with the Self-learning Modules. Therefore, if materials of poor quality are provided during this crucial period, learners' interactions with the materials while working independently would not let them acquire the necessary skills and knowledge needed to be applied to new situations. It only implies that providing quality-assured learning materials for learning engagement is a necessity for the kindergarten learners' potential development and autonomy in learning.

In addition, the process of evaluating how much learning a learner has attained during the engagement period is also challenged on difficulties encountered by the kindergarten teachers. Dynamic worksheets, or the act of finding out what a learner is able to do independently as well as can be done with adult guidance, is integral to Bruner's idea of scaffolding. In the acquisition of the said skills, kindergarten learners' participation in the assessment/worksheet process is of importance. On the other hand, in this printed modular instruction scheme, teachers find it difficult to connect with learners and to validate whether accomplished tasks or outputs are really learners' works.

These three concerns on the distribution and retrieval of self-learning modules/alternative delivery mode, the completion of module and the assessment/worksheet were the three areas considered in this study under challenges met by kindergarten teachers in the implementation of printed modular instruction.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the degree of challenges encountered by the kindergarten teachers of Tayasan District 1 and 2 Division of Negros Oriental using printed modular instruction for the first semester of the school year 2020-2021, as basis for an intervention plan.

Methodology:

A study on investigating children's readiness in Mathematics was conducted by Lee, Autry, Fox, .According to their findings that children's Mathematics readiness depended not only on the

This chapter presents the research design, the locale and respondents of the study, the research instruments, data gathering procedure, and the analytical schemes and statistical tools to be used in the analysis of data relative to the specific objectives of this study.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive method of research in determining the degree of challenges problems encountered by the kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction for the first semester of Tayasan District 1 and 2 of the division of Negros Oriental, for this school year 2020-2021. Descriptive research is based on the premise that problems can be solved, and practices improved through observation, analysis, and description. Descriptive study designs are useful for simply describing the desired characteristics of the sample that is being studied. A descriptive study may also try to generalize the findings from a representative sample to a larger target population. The common aspect between the descriptive study designs is that there is only one single sample without any comparison group (McCombes, 2019).

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the 30 kindergarten teachers from the two districts of Tayasan in which 13 of them were coming from the District 1 and the remaining 17 were coming from the District 2 during the School Year 2020-2021. Since there were only few number of respondents in the two districts of Tayasan, purposive sampling technique was considered utilizing 100% of the total population. According to Turner (2020) that Purposive Sampling is a non-probability sampling technique where researchers intentionally select participants based on specific characteristics relevant to their study.

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents. As seen in the table, there were a total of 13 kinder teachers from District 1 of Tayasan comprising 41.40% of the total population while there were a total of 17 kinder teachers from the District 2 of Tayasan comprising 58.62% of the total population. Therefore, a total of 30 respondents were considered in this study.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

No. of School District per	Population (N)	Percentage (%)	Data
District 1	13	41.40	
District 2	17	58.62	
Total	30	100.00	

Gathering Instrument

A self-made instrument will be used in determining the challenges encountered by the kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction. The questionnaire is composed of two parts. Part I of the questionnaire involves the demographic data of the teacher-respondents which includes the plantilla position, length of service and educational qualification.

Part II determines the respondents' degree of challenges by the kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction in the areas of distribution and retrieval of Self-learning modules (alternative delivery mode), completion of printed modular instruction and Assessment (worksheet). There are 10 items per area of which will be measured using the following scale: such as 5-Very High Degree, 4-High Degree, 3-Moderate Degree, 2-Low Degree, and 1-Very Low Degree.

Validity

A drafted questionnaire should always be ready for establishing validity. Validity means the degree to which a test or measuring instrument measure what is intends to measure (Good, 2015). Validity of a questionnaire can be established using a panel of experts which explore theoretical construct. This form of validity exploits how well the idea of a theoretical construct is represented in an open measure or questionnaire.

Checking of the instrument's validity will be based on the criteria set forth by Calter V. Good and Douglas F. Scates. The interpretation are as follows: Excellent (4.21-5.00), Very Good (3.41-4.20); Good (2.61-3.40), Fair (1.81-2.60), and Poor (1.00-1.80). The result of the validity was 4.5 interpreted as Excellent.

Reliability

Reliability is an extent to which a questionnaire, test, observation or any measurement procedure produces the same results on repeated trials (Bolarinwa, 2016). In short, it is the reliability of consistency of scores over time across raters. Reliability of the questionnaire is to be carried out using a pilot test. To be reliable, the obtained value of

the tests must be from 0.70 to 1.00. The reliability index of the research instrument used in this study is 0.957 interpreted as excellent. Therefore, the result of the reliability test of this study is reliable and valid.

Data Gathering Procedure

After the validity and reliability test will be administered and found out that the research instrument was valid and reliable, the researcher in the gathering data will send a letter to the Public Schools District Supervisor asking permission to conduct the study entitled "Challenges Encountered by the Kindergarten Teachers using Printed Modular Instruction: Basis for an Intervention Plan". After the approval of the PSD, the researcher will conduct the instrument to the respondents. Data will be collected through the said link. They will be organized and treated statistically for analysis and interpretation. The researcher wrote a permission letter to the school's district supervisor and district in-charge for the conduct of the study. After permission was granted, she proceeded to the administration of the questionnaires which she floated through messenger Group Chat created for such purpose. Accomplished questionnaires were collected through the researcher's email or messenger.

Data collected were organized and treated statistically for analysis and interpretation through the aid of SPSS.

Research Ethics Protocol

Participants' personal demographic information results were collected and were noted in the data capturing sheet. Informed consent via verbal communication was elicited with the respondents. They read and understood the provided information and can ask questions. Moreover, their participation was voluntary, and they were free to withdraw without giving any reasons. The respondents were assured that there would be no risks of harm will experience before, during, or after participating in the research. The data and information used in the study were treated with strict confidentiality. No statement regarding the participant's identity was disclosed unnecessarily in this study. After the data gathering, since there was no need, debriefing was not done by the researcher anymore, as cited in the Data Privacy Act.

Analytical Schemes

The analyses of the data involved in this study were descriptive and comparative analytical schemes:

Objective No. 1 which aimed to identify the profile of the respondents in terms of plantilla position, length of service and educational qualification used the descriptive analytical scheme.

Objective No. 2 which aimed to determine the degree of challenges encountered by the kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction in terms of distribution and retrieval of self-learning modules, completion of printed modular instruction and assessment (worksheet) utilized the descriptive analytical scheme.

Objective No. 3 which determined the degree of challenges encountered by the kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables employed the descriptive analytical scheme.

Objective No. 4 which unfurled if there is a significant difference in the degree of challenges encountered by the kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction when they are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables used the comparative analytical scheme.

Results and Discussion:

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain procedures to give the exact data and solution to each problem.

Profile of Respondents in Terms of Variables Plantilla Position, Length of Service, and Educational Qualification

Table 2
Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Plantilla Position	Lower (Teacher 1)	16	53.30
	Higher (Teacher 2 and above)	14	46.70
Length of Service	Shorter (Less than 4 years)	13	43.30

Educational Qualification	Longer (4 years and above)	17	56.70
	Lower (BEED)	16	53.30
	Higher (BEED with ECE units)	14	46.70
	Total	30	100.00

Table 2 presents the profiles of the respondents. In terms of plantilla position, there were 16 or 53.30 percent of Teacher 1 and 14 or 46.70 percent of Teacher 2 and above. Since Teacher 2 comprises less than the Teacher 1 respondents, it only implies that the kindergarten teachers were more designated to Teacher 1 than Teacher 2 and above in the research venue.

As to the length of services, 13, or 43.30 percent, belonged to the shorter category, or those having less than 4 years in service, and 17, or 56.70 percent, to the higher category, or those having 4 years and above. This implies that the total number of respondents was more composed of longer length of service, which is 4 years and above, than the lower length of service respondents, which is less than 4 years in service. Arlyn Cadampog's study on Professional Profile and Performance of Kindergarten Teachers in Public Schools: Inputs for a Proposed Training Program (2021) revealed that the length of service is not statistically related to performance. This implies that teaching kindergarten learners does not affect the performance of teachers based on their length of service. Furthermore, it is recommended that the Department of Education (DepEd) address the gaps between the professional profile of the Kindergarten Teachers in the districts and their performance in the schools, Arlyn Cadampog added.

In terms of educational qualification, 16 or 53.30 percent were in the lower category of those kindergarten teachers who graduated with BEEd, while 14 or 46.70 percent were in the higher category, which comprises kindergarten teachers who graduated as BEEd with ECE units. As far as the median is concerned, more teachers belong to the lower category or those teachers who graduated as BEEd due to educational qualification.

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers Using Printed Modular Instruction in the Areas of Distribution and Retrieval of Self Learning Modules, Completion of Printed Modular Instruction, and Assessments (worksheet)

Table 3

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers Using Printed Modular Instruction in the Area of Distribution and Retrieval of Self-Learning Modules

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what degree do you experience the following challenges in implementing modular learning?</i>		
Insufficiency of allocation for the purchase of supplies	4.43	High Degree
Shortage of production materials such as reams of bond papers and ink	4.47	High Degree
Inadequate binding materials	4.50	Very High Degree
Unbalanced distribution of supplies for reproduction	4.63	Very High Degree
No provision of alcohol or sanitizers at drop-off points as part of health protocols	3.80	High Degree
Unavailability of equipment for module production	3.57	High Degree
No available time for parents and guardians to get and return the self-learning modules	3.20	Moderate Degree
Malfunction of equipment	3.23	Moderate Degree
No observance of the scheduled time of self-learning module distribution and retrieval	4.57	Very High Degree
Not picked up and not returned self-learning modules	4.20	High Degree
Sub-mean	4.06	High Degree

Table 3 displays the degree of challenges kindergarten teachers encounter using printed modular instruction in the distribution and retrieval of self-learning modules. It is evident that item no. 7 got the lowest mean of 3.20 or moderate degree, while item no. 4 got the highest mean of 4.63 or very high degree.

In item no. 7 states that there is no time for parents and guardians to get and return the self-learning modules. This means that parent-teacher partnership is considered. It should be noted that engaging parents demands a deep reflexive attitude from the teacher—one that most likely develops through practice and meaningful internalization processes of knowledge. Beginning teachers must be encouraged to develop a moral stance concerning their professional responsibilities to meaningfully develop the ability and sensitivity to establish authentic partnerships with all parents (Lima & Kuusisto, 2019). Since parents act as learning facilitators in ensuring that their children are indeed learning from the materials provided, parents must collaborate with teachers (or vice-versa) in meeting the learner's goals of the children (ADEC Innovations, 2019).

On the other hand, item no. 4 states an unbalanced distribution of supplies for reproduction. The main challenge that emerged was the lack of school funding for producing and delivering modules (Dangle & Sumaong, 2020).

This contradicts the statement about the unavailability of equipment for module reproduction is accounted for as the least challenging for teachers because some kindergarten teachers have their own personal printers for module reproduction, which are otherwise provided by the school to which they are assigned. It is quite ironic that while there is a lot of printing equipment available, there has been a shortage of bond papers and ink in the local market, even leaving the division office with no choice but to import such from other countries. This confirms the findings of the study of Olamo et al. (2019) that the modular curriculum has not been effectively implemented due to some challenges.

The challenges include the fact that the facilities and materials were not available in the required quantity and quality. Moreover, in the local news, Vice President Leni Robredo echoed the concerns of some teachers' groups regarding the lack of resources and health risks in printing and distributing learning modules a day before classes start in public schools (CNN Philippines, 2020). Robredo shared the struggles of some teachers who have been burdened with the pressure of completing the distribution of printed modules, unlike the usual tradition of holding face-to-face classes.

Table 4

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers Using Printed Modular Instruction in the Area of Completion of Printed Modular Instruction

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what degree do you experience the following challenges in implementing modular learning?</i>		
No opportunity for developing social skills for learners	1.63	Low Degree
Inadequate presentations and discussions on learning content/topics presented since parents/guardians will be the ones to assist their child	1.63	Low Degree
Non-observance of correct letter writing	1.33	Very Low Degree
Non-observance of correct letter sounding	1.53	Low Degree
Unclear and unattractive illustrations and activities	1.57	Low Degree
Non-provision of materials needed to complete the tasks	1.00	Very Low Degree
No consideration of the diversity of learners and their multiple intelligences	1.27	Very Low Degree
Malfunction of equipment	1.87	Low Degree
No consideration of the diversity of learners and their multiple intelligences	1.47	Very Low Degree
Irrelevant, uninteresting, and not self-motivating activities	1.40	Very Low Degree
Sub-mean	1.45	Very Low Degree

Table 4 displays the result of the degree of challenges encountered by the kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction in the area of completion of printed modular instruction. It is evident from the table that item no. 6 got the lowest mean of 1.00, interpreted as a very low degree. This is due to the lack of materials needed to complete the tasks.

While item no. 8 got a mean of 1.87, interpreted as a low degree, which is the malfunction of equipment. Malfunction of equipment such as laptops/computers and printers that are being used in the reproduction of modules is one of the challenges of kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction since it is the first time that we are introducing this one due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

This confirms the findings of the study by Olamo et al. (2019) that the modular curriculum has not been effectively implemented due to some challenges. The challenges include the fact that the facilities and materials were not available in the required quantity and quality. Moreover, in the local news, Vice President Robredo echoed the concerns of some teachers' groups regarding the lack of resources and even health risks in printing and distributing the learning modules (CNN Philippines, 2020). The struggles of some teachers who have been burdened with the pressure of completing the distribution of printed modules, unlike the usual tradition of holding face-to-face classes.

Table 5

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers Using Printed Modular Instruction in the Area of Assessment (Worksheet)

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what degree do you experience the following challenges in the implementation of modular learning?</i>		
1. Difficulty of daily monitoring	4.70	Very High Degree
2. Difficulty in designing/planning performance tasks	4.53	Very High Degree

3. Incompleteness of record of evidence of learners' achievements	4.63	Very High Degree
4. Difficulty in creating and molding learning progress	4.63	Very High Degree
5. Absence of involvement and socialization of learners in the activity and learning process	4.53	Very High Degree
6. Failure to use a range and the right learning strategy in order to acquire a new and useful skill	4.53	Very High Degree
7. Tendency of mismatch with the curriculum standards and competencies	4.43	High Degree
8. Difficulty of quarterly monitoring	4.37	High Degree
9. Difficulty in designing/planning performance tasks	4.43	High Degree
10. Incompleteness of record of evidence of learners' achievements	4.33	High Degree
Sub-mean	4.51	Very High Degree

Table 5 displays the degree of challenges encountered by the kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction in assessment (worksheet). From the table, the incompleteness of the record of evidence of learners' achievements got a mean of 4.33, which is a high degree. Since teachers during this pandemic can no longer meet their learners personally, they only rely on the assessment (worksheet) that has been distributed to the learners; distance learning poses challenges for learners and teachers in the conduct of assessment (DO 31, 2020). These include limitations on giving feedback and the need to account for their contexts in designing, implementing, and grading the assessment tasks. Therefore, learners, teachers, and parents/guardians are reminded of the significant roles and responsibilities regarding assessment.

According to the research of Lima & Kuusisto, 2019 teachers consider families' involvement important to learners' success, recognizing that parents are positive contributors. Constant communication between the parents and the kindergarten teacher is a must to meet the expected learning outcome stipulated in our DepEd Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC).

On the other hand, item no. 1 got the highest mean of 4.70, interpreted as a very high degree. This is the difficulty of daily monitoring. This means that teachers found it very difficult to monitor their learners daily, especially kindergarten teachers in the hinterland schools where there is no available signal or even parents/guardians don't have gadgets to use in communication.

After all, according to Rahmawati et al., 2019 learning with modules will further enhance the learners' learning outcomes; that is, kindergarten teachers should be aware of the content of the modules. Furthermore, the contents of the instructional materials are basic and suitable to the level of learners and, at the same time, relevant to day-to-day activities.

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers Using Printed Modular Instruction in the Areas of Distribution and Retrieval of Self Learning Modules, Completion of Printed Modular Instruction, and Assessments (worksheet) when grouped according to Variables Plantilla Position, Length of Service, and Educational Qualification

Table 6
Degree of Challenges Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers Using Printed Modular Instruction in the Area of Distribution and Retrieval of Self-Learning Modules When Grouped According to Plantilla Position

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what degree do you experience the following challenges in the implementation of modular learning?</i>				
Insufficiency of allocation for the purchase of supplies	4.25	High Degree	4.64	Very High Degree
Shortage of production materials such as reams of bond papers and ink	4.25	High Degree	4.71	Very High Degree
Inadequate binding materials	4.31	High Degree	4.71	Very High Degree
Unbalanced distribution of supplies for reproduction	4.50	Very High Degree	4.79	Very High Degree
No provision of alcohol or sanitizers at drop-off points as part of health protocols	3.63	High Degree	4.00	High Degree
Unavailability of equipment for module production	3.44	Moderate Degree	3.71	High Degree
No available time for parents and guardians to get and return the self-learning modules	3.13	Moderate Degree	3.29	Moderate Degree
Malfunction of equipment	3.25	Moderate Degree	3.21	Moderate Degree
None observance of the scheduled time of self-learning module distribution and retrieval	4.38	High Degree	4.79	Very High Degree

Not picked up and not returned self-learning modules	3.88	High Degree	4.57	Very High Degree
Sub-mean	3.90	High Degree	4.24	High Degree

Table 6 presents the challenges encountered by kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction in distribution and retrieval when grouped according to plantilla position. In item no. 7, which states that "no available time for parents and guardians to get and return the self-learning modules," the lower group got a mean of 3.13 while the higher group got a mean of 3.29, both interpreted as a moderate degree. This connotes that kindergarten teachers have a moderate degree of challenges in terms of the teacher-parent partnership, whether it is in the lower or higher group. Since parents act as learning facilitators in ensuring that their children are indeed learning from the materials provided, it is important that parents collaborate with teachers (or vice-versa) in meeting the learner's goals of the children (ADEC Innovations, 2019).

Based on the overall findings on the degree of challenges encountered by the kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction when they are grouped according to plantilla position, regardless of whether they belonged to a lower or higher category, the results yielded an interpretation of High Degree. This finding implied that their experiences in the field of retrieval and distribution of printed materials were incomparable.

It thoroughly supports the study of Lima & Kuusisto (2019) that all teachers need to be encouraged to develop a moral stance in relation to their professional responsibilities to meaningfully develop the ability and sensitiveness to establish authentic partnerships with all parents.

Table 7

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers Using Printed Modular Instruction in the Area of Completion of Printed Modular Instruction When Grouped According to Plantilla Position

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what degree do you experience the following challenges in the implementation of modular learning?</i>				
No opportunity for developing social skills for learners	1.75	Low Degree	1.50	Low Degree
Inadequate presentations and discussions on learning content/topics presented since parents/guardians will be the ones to assist their child	1.63	Low Degree	1.64	Low Degree
Non-observance of correct letter writing	1.31	Very Low Degree	1.36	Very Low Degree
Non-observance of correct letter sounding	1.69	Low Degree	1.36	Very Low Degree
Unclear and unattractive illustrations and activities	1.63	Low Degree	1.50	Low Degree
Non-provisions of materials needed to complete the tasks	1.00	Very Low Degree	1.00	Very Low Degree
No consideration of the diversity of learners and their multiple intelligences	1.38	Very Low Degree	1.14	Very Low Degree
Malfunction of equipment	1.81	Low Degree	1.93	Low Degree
No consideration of the diversity of learners and their multiple intelligences	1.50	Low Degree	1.43	Very Low Degree
Irrelevant, uninteresting, and not self-motivating activities	1.38	Very Low Degree	1.43	Very Low Degree
Sub-mean	1.48	Very Low Degree	1.42	Very Low Degree

Table 7 reveals the degree of challenges encountered by the kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction around the completion of printed modular instruction when grouped according to plantilla position.

A closer look at the general result shows that both the lower group and higher group got the sub-mean interpretation of a very low degree, especially in item 6, which states that non-provisions of material are needed to complete the tasks. This contradicts the statement that even if DepEd is trying to provide for the needs of each kindergarten teacher, they still end up purchasing a personal printer. In fact, the Teachers Dignity Coalition lamented the difficulty that teachers must face in printing modules and shouldering the cost of equipment (CNN Philippines, 2020). Printers have a thousand reasons that can go wrong so soon after the purchase. Personal equipment, repairs, and parts replacements will have to be shouldered once again by the kindergarten teachers.

Table 8

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers Using Printed Modular Instruction in the Area of Assessment (Worksheet) When Grouped According to Plantilla Position

Items	Lower	Higher
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	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what degree do you experience the following challenges in the implementation of modular learning?</i>				
Difficulty of daily monitoring	4.63	Very High Degree	4.79	Very High Degree
Difficulty in designing/planning performance tasks	4.38	High Degree	4.71	Very High Degree
Incompleteness of record of evidence of learners' achievements	4.50	Very High Degree	4.79	Very High Degree
Difficulty in creating and molding learning progress	4.56	Very High Degree	4.71	Very High Degree
Absence of involvement and socialization of learners in the activity and learning process	4.31	High Degree	4.79	Very High Degree
Failure to use a range and the right learning strategy in order to acquire a new and useful skill	4.38	High Degree	4.71	Very High Degree
Tendency of mismatch with the curriculum standards and competencies	4.13	High Degree	4.79	Very High Degree
Difficulty of quarterly monitoring	4.00	High Degree	4.79	Very High Degree
Difficulty in designing/planning performance tasks	4.13	High Degree	4.79	Very High Degree
Incompleteness of record of evidence of learners' achievements	3.94	High Degree	4.79	Very High Degree
Sub-mean	4.29	High Degree	4.76	Very High Degree

Table 8 reveals the degree of challenges encountered by kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction around completion of printed modular instruction when grouped according to plantilla position. Looking at the general result, the lower group got a sub-mean of 4.29, interpreted as a high degree, and the higher group got a sub-mean of 4.76, a very high degree. However, they vary in item no. 10, where the lower group got 3.94 or a high degree, while the higher group got 4.79 or a very high degree. This is due to the incompleteness of the record of evidence of learners' achievements.

This is a revealing idea that is very possible in the challenges in assessment in this new normal situation. Supported in a blog published on March 14, 2020, one of the emphases on challenges of modular learning was on Correct Assessment of Learners' Work. Although such assessment is similar in face-to-face classrooms, the difficulty comes from delivering the required expectations and standards for each task (How to Overcome Challenges on Modular Learning, 2020). Moreover, online assessments are most likely open-book and are subject to the possibility of distance cheating if there is no proctor. And it is impossible in remote areas where the internet connection is very poor and/ or there is no electricity.

Table 9

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers Using Printed Modular Instruction in the Area of Distribution and Retrieval of Self-Learning Modules When Grouped According to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what degree do you experience the following challenges in the implementation of modular learning?</i>				
Insufficiency of allocation for the purchase of supplies	4.38	High Degree	4.47	High Degree
Shortage of production materials such as reams of bond papers and ink	4.54	Very High Degree	4.41	High Degree
Inadequate binding materials	4.62	Very High Degree	4.41	High Degree
Unbalanced distribution of supplies for reproduction	4.69	Very High Degree	4.59	Very High Degree
No provision of alcohol or sanitizers at drop-off points as part of health protocols	3.38	Moderate Degree	4.12	High Degree
Unavailability of equipment for module production	3.31	Moderate Degree	3.76	High Degree
No available time for parents and guardians to get and return the self-learning modules	2.77	Moderate Degree	3.53	High Degree
Malfunction of equipment	2.85	Moderate Degree	3.53	High Degree

None observance of the scheduled time of self-learning module distribution and retrieval	4.46	High Degree	4.65	Very High Degree
Not picked up and not returned self-learning modules	3.77	High Degree	4.53	Very High Degree
Sub-mean	3.88	High Degree	4.20	High Degree

Table 9 presents kindergarten teachers' challenges when using printed modular instruction in distribution and retrieval of self-learning modules when grouped according to length of service. Veering at the overall mean, both the shorter group and longer group obtained the mean score interpretation of high degree. However, they vary in item no. 7 where the lower group had 2.77 or moderate degree and 3.53 or high degree in the higher group. There is no available time for parents and guardians to return and get the self-learning modules.

Table 10

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers Using Printed Modular Instruction in the Area of Completion of Printed Modular Instruction When Grouped According to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what degree do you experience the following challenges in the implementation of modular learning?</i>				
No opportunity for developing social skills for learners	1.62	Low Degree	1.65	Low Degree
Inadequate presentations and discussions on learning content/topics presented since parents/guardians will be the ones to assist their child	1.46	Very Low Degree	1.76	Low Degree
Non-observance of correct letter writing	1.23	Very Low Degree	1.41	Very Low Degree
Non-observance of correct letter sounding	1.62	Low Degree	1.47	Very Low Degree
Unclear and unattractive illustrations and activities	1.46	Very Low Degree	1.65	Low Degree
Non-provisions of materials needed to complete the tasks	1.00	Very Low Degree	1.00	Very Low Degree
No consideration of the diversity of learners and their multiple intelligences	1.31	Very Low Degree	1.24	Very Low Degree
Malfunction of equipment	1.69	Low Degree	2.00	Low Degree
No consideration of the diversity of learners and their multiple intelligences	1.46	Very Low Degree	1.47	Very Low Degree
Irrelevant, uninteresting, and not self-motivating activities	1.31	Very Low Degree	1.47	Very Low Degree
Sub-mean	1.39	Very Low Degree	1.50	Low Degree

Table 10 reveals the degree of challenges that kindergarten teachers encounter using printed modular instruction in the completion of printed modular instruction when grouped according to length of service. Veering at the overall mean, both shorter and longer groups in terms of length of service take this challenge to a low degree with the sub-mean score of 1.39 and 1.50, respectively. However, they vary in item no. 2, where the shorter group had 1.46 or very low degree 1.76 or low degree in the longer group. This is due to the inadequate presentations and discussions on learning content/topics presented since parents/guardians will be the ones to assist their children. This is the result of the strong parent-teacher partnership. Regardless of how short or long the kindergarten teacher was in service, both acted and acted as effective teachers.

ADEC Innovations (2019) supports it, which states that since parents act as learning facilitators in ensuring that their children are indeed learning from the materials provided, it is important that parents collaborate with teachers (or vice-versa) in meeting the learner's goals of the children (ADEC Innovations, 2019).

Table 11

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers Using Printed Modular Instruction in the Area of Assessment (Worksheet) When Grouped According to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what degree do you experience the following challenges in the implementation of modular learning?</i>				
1. Difficulty of daily monitoring	4.69	Very High Degree	4.71	Very High Degree

2. Difficulty in designing/planning performance tasks	4.62	Very High Degree	4.47	High Degree
3. Incompleteness of record of evidence of learners' achievements	4.77	Very High Degree	4.53	Very High Degree
4. Difficulty in creating and molding learning progress	4.77	Very High Degree	4.53	Very High Degree
5. Absence of involvement and socialization of learners in the activity and learning process	4.46	High Degree	4.59	Very High Degree
6. Failure to use a range and the right learning strategy in order to acquire a new and useful skill	4.46	High Degree	4.59	Very High Degree
7. Tendency of mismatch with the curriculum standards and competencies	4.23	High Degree	4.59	Very High Degree
8. Difficulty of quarterly monitoring	4.23	High Degree	4.47	Very High Degree
9. Difficulty in designing/planning performance tasks	4.23	High Degree	4.59	Very High Degree
10. Incompleteness of record of evidence of learners' achievements	3.92	High Degree	4.65	Very High Degree
Sub-mean	4.44	High Degree	4.57	Very High Degree

Table 11 shows the degree of challenges encountered by the kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction in the area assessment (worksheet) when grouped according to length of service. Veering closely at the sub-mean, the shorter group got 4.44, interpreted as a high degree, while the longer group got 4.57, interpreted as a very high degree. However, when each result was considered, it is in item no. 10 on the incompleteness of record of evidence of learners' achievements where the difference of the mean scores of shorter in the length of service and longer in the length of service was greater; shorter group with 3.92 or high degree and longer group with 4.65 or very high degree.

It is evident that both groups in the length of service have a high degree of challenges in the incompleteness of record of evidence of learners' achievements; due to the non-traditional way of learning during this pandemic, teachers do not have the opportunity to teach and see the output of their learners. This is true in the challenge of assessment, which is that teachers might also feel the need to formatively assess students' learning progress to provide personalized feedback (Laghigna, 2020).

Table 12

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers Using Printed Modular Instruction in the Area of Distribution and Retrieval of Self-Learning Modules When Grouped According to Educational Qualification

Items	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
<i>To what degree do you experience the following challenges in the implementation of modular learning?</i>				
Insufficiency of allocation for the purchase of supplies	4.44	High Degree	4.43	High Degree
Shortage of production materials such as reams of bond papers and ink	4.50	Very High Degree	4.43	High Degree
Inadequate binding materials	4.56	Very High Degree	4.43	High Degree
Unbalanced distribution of supplies for reproduction	4.63	Very High Degree	4.64	Very High Degree
No provision of alcohol or sanitizers at drop-off points as part of health protocols	3.50	High Degree	4.14	High Degree
Unavailability of equipment for module production	3.44	Moderate Degree	3.71	High Degree
no available time for parents and guardians to get and return the self-learning modules	2.94	Moderate Degree	3.50	High Degree
Malfunction of equipment	3.00	Moderate Degree	3.50	High Degree
None observance of the scheduled time of self-learning module distribution and retrieval	4.50	Very High Degree	4.64	Very High Degree

Not picked up and not returned self-learning modules	3.81	High Degree	4.64	Very High Degree
Sub-mean	3.93	High Degree	4.21	High Degree

Table 12 shows the degree of challenges encountered by the kindergarten teachers using printed modular instruction in the area of distribution and retrieval of printed modules when grouped according to educational qualification. Veering closely at the sub-mean, the lower group got 3.93, interpreted as a high degree, while the higher group got 4.21, interpreted as a high degree. However, when each result was considered, it is in item no. 7 on no available time for parents and guardians to get and return the self-learning modules; lower group with 2.94 or moderate degree and higher group with 3.50 or high degree.

Conclusion:

The study found that kindergarten teachers experienced a moderate to high degree of challenges in implementing printed modular instruction, particularly in the areas of distribution and retrieval of self-learning modules and assessment through worksheets, while challenges related to the completion of modules were generally low. Most respondents held lower plantilla positions, had shorter service lengths, and lower educational qualifications. Regardless of these categories, challenges in distribution, retrieval, and assessment remained consistently high across groups, indicating systemic issues such as equipment malfunctions, supply shortages, and difficulties in daily monitoring due to the absence of face-to-face classes. Significant differences in the degree of challenges were observed when grouped by plantilla position, length of service, and educational attainment, suggesting that teachers' experiences vary based on their professional profiles. The study concludes that these challenges are serious and persistent, warranting immediate action. It recommends that future research include more diverse grouping variables, that school leaders and DepEd coordinate with local government units for logistical support and resource provision, and that school heads and teachers use action research to continuously investigate and address recurring problems in printed modular instruction.

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